

Density-functional theory predicts relative racemate versus enantiopure crystal solubility

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Abstract

Isolation of chiral molecules as pure enantiomers remains a fundamental challenge in chemical research. Enantioselective enrichment through preferential crystallization is an efficient method to achieve enantiopure solutions, but its applicability depends on the relative stability of the enantiopure and racemic crystal forms. In this work, we show that, using a simple thermodynamic model and first-principles density-functional theory calculations, it is possible to predict the difference in solubility between the enantiopure and racemic solid phases. This approach uses dispersion-corrected density functionals and is capable of accurately predicting the enantiomeric excess to within ca. 10% of experimental measurements on average. The accuracy of the exchange-hole dipole moment (XDM) model of dispersion enables the viability of the proposed method.

Chirality has fascinated chemists ever since Pasteur explained the phenomenon at a molecular level by completing the first racemic resolution in 1848.¹ The efficient resolution of chiral mixtures into pure enantiomers has great relevance both in fundamental chemistry (e.g. explaining the origin of homochirality in biological molecules²⁻⁴) as well as in the pharmaceutical and agrochemical industries.^{5,6} One of the most efficient methods of accomplishing enantiopurification of a scalemic mixture is prefer-

ential crystallization.⁷ However, only a small fraction of chiral organic molecules can be separated using this technique⁸ because the target compound needs to crystallize in a conglomerate phase, in which the enantiopure crystals are more stable than corresponding racemic solid.

Conglomerate-forming compounds are relatively rare, as most molecules (~90% of chiral crystals) form a racemic crystalline solid (the racemate phase) made up of both enantiomers. This acute but subtle difference between compounds forming conglomerate and racemate phases is best illustrated by examining the ternary phase diagrams for the equilibria between the crystalline and solution-phase enantiomers, shown in 1. Conglomerates (1a) have ternary phase diagrams involving solely enantiopure crystals and a solution phase. In contrast, samples forming a racemic compound (1b), have an additional racemic solid phase present.

While classical preferential separation requires a stable conglomerate phase, new methods have exploited the difference in solubility of the enantiopure and racemic phases to achieve enantiopurification.^{9,10} In either case, the optimization of crystallization techniques to effect separation of enantiomers requires knowledge of solubility equilibria for both the enantiopure and racemic solid phases. The relative solubility difference can be determined experimentally by measuring the ratio of the D and L enantiomers in the saturated solution of a scalemic

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system, expressed as the enantiomeric excess. This is possible because the solubility of both the D and L enantiopure crystals are equal; at equilibrium the solution phase of conglomerate-forming compounds will always contain equal concentrations of both enantiomers (e.e. = 0). Alternatively, saturated solutions in contact with both racemic and eniopure crystals will contain an excess of one enantiomer because the racemic and enantiopure crystals have different solubilities. Therefore, measurement of the solution-phase enantiomeric excess allows researchers to categorize compounds in terms of the tie line shown on the phase diagram in 1b.

While this measurement appears straightforward, accurate e.e. measurement requires an appropriate analytical technique, such as chiral stationary phase HPLC or NMR in a chiral solvent. In addition, sufficient samples of both the racemic and enantiopure crystal phases must be obtained to create saturated solutions at equilibrium. Thus the limitation of experimental analytics, coupled with the need for pure samples, can cause serious limitations. It would thus be extremely valuable if theory could be used to predict the relative solubility between the two crystalline forms of target molecules. Because the energies of the two crystalline lattices determine their relative solubilities, we thus need to be able to accurately calculate the small energy difference between the enantiopure and racemic crystals to predict the solution-phase e.e.

Until recently, density-functional theory (DFT) methods could not provide accurate treatment of intermolecular interactions, due to neglect of London dispersion,¹¹ the force responsible for long-range attractive interactions between non-polar chemical species.¹² There are now several successful DFT-based dispersion approaches in common use,^{13–18} including the exchange-hole dipole moment (XDM) dispersion model of Becke and Johnson.^{19,20} The XDM method has been shown to double the accuracy of other dispersion corrections for molecular crystals²¹ giving heats of sublimation to within ca. 1 kcal/mol on average. In this work, we apply the XDM method to prediction

of amino-acid chiral eutectic points (points E and E' in figure 1), which is as an even more sensitive test of theory due to the very small inherent energy differences. We show that XDM predicts energy differences with an accuracy much higher than 1 kcal/mol, probably thanks to error cancellation.

Figure 1: Sketch of the ternary phase diagram of a chiral compound for conglomerate-forming (a) and racemate (b) crystals.

The enantiomeric excess in solution can be predicted by considering the equilibria at the eutectic point (E and E' in figure 1). We assume an excess of the L enantiomer, corresponding to the right side of the racemate phase diagram. At the eutectic, three phases coexist in equilibrium: a saturated solution, enantiopure solid $L_{(s)}$, and racemate solid, $DL_{(s)}$. For the purpose of our theoretical treatment, we also consider the gas-phase molecules, which at a given temperature and volume are related to the solid and solvated species by the Helmholtz free energies of sublimation (ΔF_{sub}) and of solvation (ΔF_{solv}), respectively.

Because the solution is saturated, the solubility products are

$$K_{sp}(L) = [L] = \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta F_{sub}(L) + \Delta F_{solv}}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$K_{sp}(DL) = [D][L] = \exp\left(-2\frac{\Delta F_{sub}(DL) + \Delta F_{solv}}{RT}\right) \quad (4)$$

The conglomerate-forming and racemate crystals will have different sublimation energies. However, in an achiral solvent, the two enantiomers have identical solvation energies. This fact is what ultimately enables the accurate calculation of the enantiomeric excess. After some algebra, it can be shown that the e.e. in solution is

$$ee = \frac{[L] - [D]}{[L] + [D]} = \frac{\beta^2 - 1}{\beta^2 + 1} \quad (5)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta F_{sub}(L) - \Delta F_{sub}(DL)}{RT}\right) \\ &= \exp\left(\frac{E(L) - E(DL)}{RT}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where E is the electronic energy (coming directly from the DFT calculation) and we assume that the vibrational contributions to the sublimation free energy are equal for both crystals. This assumption introduces an error that is in the order of a few kJ/mol,^{22,23} but is standard in the treatment of the related problems of polymorph ranking¹¹ and crystal structure prediction.²⁴ Successful application of the methods devised to tackle problems in these fields also rely on accurate molecular crystal energetics.

The accuracy of this simple model can be demonstrated by using available experimental heats of formation. For example, in the case of alanine, ΔH_f° is -563.63 kJ/mol for the DL phase and -561.24 kJ/mol for the L phase.²⁵⁻²⁷ Using this data, the e.e. from our model is 74.6%, to be compared with the experimental value of 60.4%.²⁸ Similarly for leucine, ΔH_f° is -637.56 kJ/mol for the enantiopure phase and -640.70 kJ/mol for the DL phase.^{25,27} This gives a predicted e.e. of 85.3%, to be compared with the experimental value of 87.9%.²⁸ Unfortunately, such careful calorimetric measurements of the heats of formation are not frequently available for the L and DL phases at the same time and, in general, we must turn to density-functional theory to predict the relative energetics of the two crystal phases.

If the structures of the enantiopure and racemic crystals are known and the solvent is achiral, it is straightforward to calculate the

e.e. at the eutectic by computing the relative energy difference between the two crystals using DFT-XDM and applying equations 5 and 6. We will show that, because of the exponential in equation 6, the enantiomeric excess is extremely sensitive to the predicted energy difference between the two crystals and the range of 0-95% e.e. is spanned by only a 4.5 kJ/mol energy difference. Therefore, accurate prediction of the e.e. is an extremely challenging test for dispersion-corrected DFT. Previous applications of dispersion-corrected DFT literature²⁹ have focused solely on determining which of the conglomerate and racemate phases are more stable.

In order to test the our theoretical procedure, we considered a subset of the proteinogenic amino acids, for which solvent-free single-crystal X-ray crystal structures are available.³⁰ We assume (except where explicitly investigated) that the crystal structure obtained in the preferential crystallization is the same as the one reported in the database. For all crystals, the cell geometries and atomic positions were relaxed using the B86b exchange functional³¹ with PBE correlation³² and XDM dispersion. The vibrational effects on the crystal geometries are neglected. Calculations were performed with the Quantum Espresso program^{33,34} (available under a free license and implements XDM in the development version) using the Projector Augmented Waves (PAW) method³⁵ and the plane-waves/pseudopotentials approach. All crystals were calculated using a $4 \times 4 \times 4$ \mathbf{k} -point grid and a 80 Ry cutoff energy, as in previous work.²¹

The eutectic points for a series of amino acids were measured experimentally to provide reference data to examine the predictive capability of the XDM method. For each amino acid, three scalemic mixtures consisting of different initial enantiomeric excess (e.e.) were created by either mixing pure enantiomers (D + L amino acids) or a single enantiomer with a racemic material (L + rac amino acid). Each sample was treated with a small volume of solvent to produce saturated suspensions, which were stirred at 25°C overnight. Aliquots of the suspension were withdrawn and filtered via cen-

trifugation. The enantiomeric excess of the solution phase was measured by chiral HPLC-MS on the underivatized amino acid samples directly from the filtration. This aliquoting process was repeated daily over four days to ensure the sample had reached equilibrium. The reported eutectic point is the average of the solution-phase e.e. for the three scalemic mixtures for each amino acid.

Table 1: Solution-phase enantiomeric excess of selected amino acids obtained with the B86bPBE-XDM method and compared with experimental data from (a) previous literature²⁸ or (b) the present work. The calculated energy difference per molecule between the enantiopure and racemic crystals (in kJ/mol) is also shown.

Amino acid	DFT ΔE	DFT e.e.	Expt. e.e.
Serine	17.221	100.0	100.0 ^a
Histidine	4.209	93.5	93.7 ^a
Leucine	3.971	92.2	87.9 ^a
Alanine	2.017	67.1	60.4 ^a
Cysteine	2.113	69.2	58.4 ^b
Tyrosine	2.180	70.6	51.7 ^b
Valine	1.807	62.3	44.1 ^b
Proline	-0.791	0.0	44.4 ^b
Aspartic acid	-1.996	0.0	0.7 ^b
Glutamic acid	-8.665	0.0	0.7 ^b

Theoretical and experimental e.e. and energies are collected in 1. Using the XDM dispersion model, the solution-phase chiral eutectics are predicted to be in very good agreement with the experimental data for all of aminoacids except proline. The mean absolute error of the calculated e.e. results is 9.9% relative to experiment.

While the predicted eutectic points for most amino acids investigated are in good agreement with the observed values, two cases stand out and merit further discussion. First, DFT-XDM predicts that the enantiopure crystal phase of proline is more stable (zero e.e.). Initially, we hypothesized that a solvate crystal may have been forming in situ²⁸ but the X-ray diffraction powder pattern of the solids isolated from

Figure 2: Dependence of the enantiomeric excess on the energy difference between racemate and conglomerate phases ($\Delta E = E(L) - E(DL)$) according to our model (black line). The experimental e.e. graphed against our DFT energy differences are shown as blue data points.

the DMSO solution matched the reported values for the racemic and enantiopure crystals. The probable cause for the discrepancy is that the enantiomeric excess is extremely sensitive to the predicted energy difference between the two crystals in that particular region, as shown in 2. The errors in the calculated e.e. values increase for the racemates going down the table and are largest for the steepest portion of the concentration versus energy curve. Thus, while the proline result is in error by 40%, this represents an energy error of only 1.84 kJ/mol, demonstrating that XDM is actually giving a relatively accurate energy difference between the enantiopure and racemic crystal phases.

The second case where there was a large discrepancy between theory and experiment is isoleucine, where DFT calculations predicted an e.e. value of 93.2% compared with the experimental value of 51.7%. Careful investigation by HPLC-MS (the chromatogram is shown in the supporting information) revealed that our sample contained both the natural isoleucine as well as a minor amount of the allo-isoleucine diastereomer, which can co-crystallize with the isoleucine enantiomers. The solution phase enantiomeric excess does not represent the true

relative solubility, as the presence of the minor diastereomer alters the solid-solution equilibrium. Thus, the theoretical and experimental data should not be directly compared (and the isoleucine point is not shown in 2) since the effect of the allo diastereomer can not be captured by the calculations. This example illustrates how theory can help direct experiment by identifying situations where the equilibrium is complicated by factors for which our simple two-state thermodynamic model does not account.

In summary, we have shown that a simple theoretical model combined with state-of-the-art dispersion-corrected density functional theory calculations can be used to predict, using exclusively the knowledge of the crystal structures, the enantiomeric excess at the chiral eutectic of a scalemic solution in contact with the conglomerate and racemate crystal phases. This work validates the use of DFT-XDM to guide the choice of compounds for enantiomeric enrichment via selective crystallization.^{9,10} In addition, the calculation of the enantiomeric excess at the chiral eutectic point is shown to be an exquisitely sensitive test of theoretical methods for intermolecular interactions in the solid phase. The XDM method achieves good agreement with experiment (to within 10% on average), despite the highly non-linear energetic dependence of the enantiomeric excess.

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Supporting Information Available: Experimental procedures for the measurement of the chiral eutectic point by HPLC is discussed.

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